

BINARY BRUSHES: A NOVEL APPROACH TOWARDS ENHANCED INTERFACIAL TUNABILITY IN MULTIFUNCTIONAL POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

High surface energy nanoparticles are found to phase separate in organic polymer matrices, thereby compromising on promised property enhancements of the resulting polymer nanocomposites. One approach taken to alleviate this incompatibility is to graft polymer chains onto the particle surface. Yet, conventional homopolymer ($\chi=0$) monomodal brush grafted particles have a narrow window for achieving good dispersions due to a delicate balance between the enthalpic screening of particle cores and entropic wettability of the grafted brush. A brush with low surface coverage (σ) exposes the particle surface, leading to the self assembly of fillers into anisotropic string and sheet like morphologies [1]. On the other hand, a high graft density brush excludes matrix chains (autophobic dewetting) causing an isotropic nonzero entropic surface tension at the interface. This leads to the agglomeration of particles even in the absence of excess enthalpic interaction [2].

An approach to decouple this enthalpic and entropic balance is to use two different brush populations: a densely grafted short brush for enthalpic shielding of the core and a sparsely grafted long brush encouraging favorable brush penetration [5]. These populations could be chemically identical (bimodal) or different (mixed), in which case the short population can be independently used to introduce desired functionality. These binary brushes have been synthesized on a multitude of surfaces, but have mostly found use as environmentally responsive systems to various solvent conditions.

Bimodal PDMS brush modifications of high-refractive-index (RI) nanoparticles using a “grafting to” technique were shown useful in developing millimeter thick transparent high RI silicone nanocomposites for use in advanced LED encapsulation [3]. The authors also developed a predictive tool for the dispersion states of these particles building on a previous reported model [4].

In this work, we demonstrate the effectiveness of the binary brush approach, through a systematic study of quasi-equilibrium dispersions and mechanical properties in homopolymer thermoplastic polystyrene nanocomposites.

2. Homopolymer Polystyrene Bimodal Brush Graft Particles

We have developed a novel Consecutive Reversible Addition-Fragmentation Chain Transfer Polymerization technique (RAFT) for the grafting of binary brushes [5]. This robust technique offers excellent control over composition, molecular weights and graft densities of the individual populations.

A systematic study of the mechanical properties and dispersion of bimodal (Long: 100 kg/mol, $\sigma=0.05$ and 0.1 ch/nm² and Short: 7 Kg/mol $\sigma=0.18$ ch/nm²) polystyrene (PS) grafted 15nm Silica in a 100 Kg/mol matrix PS is performed. The dispersions and elastic moduli of these particles are compared with composites made from traditional monomodal-brush-grafted fillers with identical chain molecular weights and graft densities (100 kg/mol, $\sigma=0.05$ and 0.1 ch/nm²). The monomodal fillers are found to aggregate into strings and sheets in this range of σ

and molecular weights, as suggested by Akcora et al [1]. The bimodal fillers, on the other hand, reveal a marked improvement in dispersion as shown in Figure 1. This is attributed to the dense brush induced lowering of the van der Waals attraction between particles. The lowered attraction leads to an expanded window of dispersion in the given parameter space. These bimodal-brush-grafted particles are found to remain well dispersed even in a dewetting 190 kg/mol PS matrix.

The hardness and elastic moduli of the bimodal systems, obtained by nanoindentation, also show a remarkable improvement over the monomodal counterparts, superior to values suggested by the Halpin-Tsai mixing rule (Figure 2). This improvement is attributed to the superior dispersion in the bimodal systems.

It is found that the glass transition temperature in the $\sigma = 0.05 \text{ ch/nm}^2$ bimodal-brush-grafted fillers, remains unchanged with particle loading, whereas the $\sigma = 0.10 \text{ ch/nm}^2$ bimodal fillers cause a decrease in Tg of 3 °C at 10 weight % Silica. This observation suggests that the lower density 0.05 ch/nm^2 long chain offers better entanglement with the matrix, which is identified as the cause for the improved elastic modulus of the 0.05 ch/nm^2 bimodal fillers embedded composite. Accordingly the 0.1 ch/nm^2 particles show a lower enhancement due to the poorly bonded interface between the brush and matrix.

3. Mixed Brush Graft Particles.

Additionally, we studied the dispersion of mixed-brush-grafted SiO_2 nanoparticles (Long: 100 kg/mol, $\sigma=0.067$ and Short: 10 Kg/mol $\sigma=0.18 \text{ ch/nm}^2$) in PMMA. From preliminary work we find these particles are well dispersed in PMMA (100 kg/mol and 300 kg/mol) even though the short PS brush is incompatible with the matrix. This suggests that the short brush purely screens core-core attractions, lowering the proclivity to agglomerate. We therefore envision functional systems with a matrix compatible (MC) long brush and a densely grafted short brush with a desired functionality.

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Figure 1. Enhanced dispersion of bimodal (Right) PS ($\sigma_{\text{long}}: 0.10 \text{ ch/nm}^2$) graft SiO_2 PS nanocomposite over monomodal (Left) PS graft SiO_2 .

Figure 2. Normalized Modulus of the various PS graft SiO_2 in PS Matrix systems